

ORAL LANGUAGE TEACHING IN AFRICAN LANGUAGE AS HOME LANGUAGE AT THE FURTHER EDUCATION AND TRAINING PHASE: AN ANALYSIS OF HOW PRACTICES ARE EVOLVING

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Abstract

The use of an African language in an Action Research program offered as a part of a continuing teacher development certificate program is the subject of this article. The article begins by discussing the function of African languages in teacher preparation and how they might be taught as a means of improving learners' epistemic access to course material at the Further Education and Training Phase. It also discusses how educators view the mother tongue's place in their own professional development and pedagogy. Additionally, the paper makes the case that if mother tongue-based bilingual education (MTBBE) is to be implemented successfully, then Professional development (PD) interventions and investments in African languages are essential. Nonetheless, one of the most obvious goals for mother tongue based bilingual education (MTBBE) in South Africa is to match the languages of teacher preparation with the languages of instruction. The New Curriculum Statement (NCS) is being incorporated into teaching practices through ongoing efforts, although the emphasis of the training is not on the epistemological and pedagogical development of teachers in terms of conceptual understanding, original thought, and inventiveness. However, interventions in professional development (PD) are seen as a way for South African educators to progress their teaching credentials, and improve their subject-matter competence, and eventually raise learners' achievement. It comes to the conclusion that in order for MTTBE to be realized at the Further Education and Training Phase, there must be adjustments made to institutional language regulations, transformations in language attitudes, staffing increases, and curriculum-wide resources in teaching and learning materials.

Keywords: Further Education and Training Phase, mother tongue-based bilingual education, African languages

1. INTRODUCTION

Professional development (PD) interventions are viewed as a means by which educators in South Africa can obtain more advanced teaching credentials, enhance their subject-matter expertise and competencies, and ultimately boost the achievement of learners (Department of Basic Education & Department of Higher Education and Training, 2011).

Research conducted over the past 20 years on professional development interventions shows that educators rarely alter their methods of instruction, even in the face of initiatives to improve their credentials and offer courses for professional development in a variety of areas (Adler & Reed 2000; Bertram 2011; Fleisch 2016;

Meyer & Abel 2015). The PD interventions have drawn criticism for their generic designs and disregard for the demands of educators or the setting when it comes to teaching language and literacy at the Further Education and Training Phase (FETP) (Murriss 2014). According to Stoffelsma (2019), the majority of programs appear to use Western paradigms that have not been experimentally validated in contexts in the global south. Research on professional development has shown that FETP teachers' participation in language, or literacy interventions appears to have little to no effect on the way they teach in township and rural schools (Blease & Condy 2014; Brodie, Lelliott & Davis 2002). Considering this, this article provides insights into the oral language instruction of a FETP teacher during a formal professional development intervention, allowing readers to better comprehend the program's impact on the instructor's teaching style in a township school.

The Department of Basic Education [DBE] (2011), states that the Curriculum Assessment Policy Statements (CAPS) link the development of listening, speaking, reading, and writing abilities with the teaching of language and literacy in home language (HL). It is evident from the school curriculum paper that teaching language skills explicitly to late-grade learners has several advantages. According to academics (Fleisch 2008; Murriss & Thompson 2016; National Education Evaluation and Development Unit [NEEDU] 2013), kids who do not master these abilities by the end of Grade 7 are more likely to have difficulties in their future academic endeavours. Murriss (2014), claims that although CAPS is based on social constructivism ideas, the majority of FETP teachers lack the necessary pedagogical expertise or are unable to implement these principles. The teaching and learning of FETP reading, terminology, and writing abilities as the Murriss (2014) claims that although CAPS is based on social constructivism ideas, the majority of FETP teachers lack the necessary pedagogical expertise or are unable to implement these principles. The teaching and learning of FETP reading, phonics, vocabulary, and writing abilities at the FP have been the subject of much research (Cilliers & Bloch 2018; Pretorius 2014; Sibanda & Baxen 2018; Spaul & Hoadley 2017). On the other hand, there isn't much research on oral language instruction or how PD therapies affect oral language teaching methods. This gap is filled by this case study. have been the subject of much research (Cilliers & Bloch 2018; Pretorius 2014; Sibanda & Baxen 2018; Spaul & Hoadley 2017). On the other hand, there isn't much research on oral language instruction or how PD therapies affect oral language teaching methods. This gap is filled by this case study.

A variety of structured pedagogical interventions, including the Gauteng Primary Literacy and Mathematics Strategy (GPLMS) in Gauteng, the Primary School Reading Improvement Programme (PSRIP) in North West and Mpumalanga provinces, and the Early Grade Reading Study (EGRS) in South Africa, have been successfully implemented by the Department of Basic Education (DBE) in South Africa. These programs are designed to fulfill the vision and mission of the DBE, which include raising the percentage of late graders who can read and write fluently in HL and EFAL, improving instructional practices, and improving learner outcomes (De Clercq & Shalem 2015; Kotze, Fleish & Taylor 2018). According to related classroom studies conducted in the Free State province, prior to these interventions, most teachers relied on conventional methods like choral or rote learning and stuck to well-known discourses during classroom interactions (NEEDU 2014; Prinsloo et al. 2015). Instructors take on "authoritarian roles doing most of the talking," assigning a few readers to themselves or encouraging active participation in vocabulary or writing exercises (Hoadley 2012:189). These results are consistent with similar projects in KwaZulu-Natal (KZN), the Eastern Cape, and the Western Cape (Spaul & Hoadley 2017). All this research seems to agree that professional development interventions should help teachers become more proficient language and literacy instructors at the FETP.

Over the past 20 years, South African learners have consistently performed poorly on internationally administered literacy examinations (Spaul & Hoadley 2017). 78% of South African youths hardly understand what they are reading, according to the 2016 Progress International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) (Howie et al. 2017). The results corroborate a pre-PIRLS study conducted by Spaul & Hoadley (2017), which found that 58% of Grade 4 students were unable to read texts in either their HL or second language fluently or decode them. Despite the fact that South Africa's government has been allocating a bigger portion of its budget to education than any other African nation over the past 20 years, these results are also consistent with the findings of the country's own Annual National Assessment (ANA) (DBE 2016). The DBE regularly cites a variety of reasons for pupils performing poorly on international and local assessments, including inadequate teaching strategies, low socioeconomic status (SES) in rural or township communities, inadequate language and literacy knowledge among FP teachers, and other complex national issues (DBE 2016). Specifically, scientific evidence indicates that learners' subpar language and literacy outcomes are mostly caused by FETP teachers' insufficiently conceptualized language expertise (DBE 2016; Fleisch 2008;

Pretorius 2014). Furthermore, research continues to raise concerns about what educators learn and how professional development programs affect language and literacy teaching methods (DBE 2016; Kotze et al. 2019). Historical accounts attribute the apartheid educational system, which provided distinct curricula for different racial groups, in part to the low language proficiency of its learners. The post-apartheid bimodal performances, in which 70% of learners perform poorly in rural regions while 30% of wealthy students continue to accomplish within the expected grade, are formed by these historical systems. These contextual variations were not considered in the initial post-apartheid school curriculum, which was an outcomes-based, learner-centered approach, nor did it offer a clear outline for teaching English language and literacy. Accordingly, many of the inadequately qualified FETP instructors still have difficulty implementing the school curriculum in addition to their own English language ability in the Free State and Northwest provinces, regions that have seen decades of high rates of unemployment and poverty, effective professional development for teachers is seen as one strategy to improve literacy instruction (Fleisch 2008; NEEDU 2013). Studies indicate that the improvement of children's literacy can potentially alleviate poverty by promoting positive and sustainable growth, which in turn raises living conditions (Nag, Snowling & Asfaha 2016; Rule & Land 2017). Considering this, the paper concentrates on the oral language instruction provided by one teacher in a Free State township school. The paper examines the educator's methods, interactions, and resource utilization to advance the oral language competency of her second-grade learners. The primary goal was to obtain information about how, or if, instructional techniques changed while she was enrolled in the Advanced Certificate in Education (ACE) program. What changes did the teacher's utilization of materials and spoken language instruction undergo in the eighteen months that she was engaged in the ACE program?

This qualitative study is guided by three main ideas: the communicative approach to teaching home language (HL), teacher professional growth, and successful professional development interventions. Data was analyzed using the HL teaching guidelines specified in the language ACE program's targeted curriculum (Kimathi 2017). Since the study is a case study, we are unable to generalize any of the conclusions we have made. Nonetheless, the knowledge gained from these insights advances the field of teaching HL to educators in comparable settings or to those who have restricted access to in-service training. The paper provides insightful information for those who plan language and literacy professional development programs in South Africa and in comparable settings. Pseudonyms were utilized in this case selection process to protect participant and school confidentiality. The participant received consent letters in accordance with DBE and university ethics guidelines.

2. AFRICAN LANGUAGES TAUGHT AS HOME LANGUAGES ACCORDING TO THE CURRICULUM

"African languages" refers to a concept used to categorize languages spoken on the African continent regionally rather than linguistically.

- The term "Further Education and Training Phase," or "FETP," refers to Grades 10 through 12.
- "Home Language" refers to the language that a person thinks in and that they initially learn by socialization at home.
- The term "Language of Learning and Teaching (LoLT)" refers to the language that a school's governing board selects after consulting with parents. Teachers employ this terminology for both teaching and assessment.

3. CONSEQUENCES FOR AFRICAN LANGUAGES' GRADUAL INTRODUCTION

The Incremental Introduction of African Languages (IIAL) policy aims to guarantee that all non-African speakers of home languages speak African languages. It does this by:

- promoting and supporting the use of African languages in the classroom for all students.
- enhancing the use of African languages at the level of home language.
- Enhancing the ability to speak and use the once neglected African languages (at the First Additional Language level).
- boosting parental self-assurance in their kids' capacity to select their own languages.

- expanding all students' access to languages outside of Afrikaans and English.
- and fostering social cohesiveness by expanding chances for African languages to flourish as an important means of comprehending cultural legacies. Gradually, starting in Grade 1 in 2015, the IIAL policy will be adopted until Grade 12, when it will be implemented in 2026. 2013 (DOB).

4. CONSEQUENCES FOR THE GRADUAL ADOPTION OF AFRICAN LANGUAGES

4.1 Promotion and Program Prerequisite

The National Policy Pertaining to the Programme and Promotion Requirements (NPPPPR) of the National Curriculum Statement Grades R–12 is impacted by the Incremental Introduction of African Languages (IIAL).

4.2 Availability of Resources

There are resource implications for teaching African languages at the First Additional Language level as well as for the gradual introduction of these languages. For all official languages, there are workbooks and the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statements (CAPS) from the Department of Basic Education accessible for both the Home and First Additional Language levels. Textbooks and readers for Home Language are available in all official languages through the National Catalogue. In order to facilitate the gradual introduction of African languages at the First Additional Language level, the Department of Basic Education will collaborate with publishers to create a list of authorized textbooks.

4.3 Availability of Teachers

Every learner must offer an African language at the First Additional Language level in order to participate in the Incremental Introduction of African Languages (IIAL). This essentially means that an African language instructor should be employed by every school. The post-provisioning standard for advancing African languages varies by province. In provinces with fewer official languages, it would be easier, and in provinces with more official languages, it would be more difficult. This holds true for both rural and urban (cosmopolitan) environments. It is anticipated that just one African language will be chosen as an HL subject in a rural setting. However, more than one African language can be chosen for this function in an urban or cosmopolitan setting. Schools will choose their preferred language to reflect the "language majority" of learners based on the demographics of the learner body and the school community.

4.4 Funding ramifications

Funding considerations include hiring more personnel to teach a third language, providing textbooks, readers, and workbooks, and offering training and reskilling programs. The National Treasury will be approached for further funding to help with the gradual introduction of African languages.

4.5 Observing and assessing

A bottom-up strategy should be used for observing and assessing starting at the school level and ending with the Department of Basic Education. At the provincial level, district reports on the gradual implementation must be combined. For the purpose of informing national planning and policy choices, the Department of Basic Education must receive consolidated reports. The following are important aspects of monitoring: (a) staffing and resource availability; (b) staffing and resource usage; (c) difficulties in implementation; (d) implications for evaluation and advancement; (e) efficacy of training; and (f) requirements in the future.

Many of the recommendations in recent research reports either implicitly or explicitly speak to the strengthening of African language teaching to improve learning outcomes. The NEEDU report applauds the incremental introduction of an African language: "The planned introduction of an African language, other than Afrikaans, for all learners is a positive policy in the interests of nation building."

In conclusion, it is important to highlight the following: • The results of the ANA, PIRLS, TIMSS, SAQMEC, and NSC have repeatedly confirmed that poor language proficiency and utility are a major contributing factor to South Africa's poor learning outcomes; • Very little, if anything, has been done to address this ongoing issue by institutions, larger civil society, or the education sector up to this point.

4.6 Teacher professional development activities for conceptual understanding

Day (1999) and Desimone (2009) define professional development interventions as educational opportunities and initiatives aimed at enhancing instructors' expertise and instructional strategies. The results of professional development activities are influenced by various factors, including the social histories, peer

groups, teaching preferences, school atmosphere, external activity quality, and larger policies of the instructors (Fraser et al. 2007). Teachers can obtain a variety of skills via professional development events, depending on the situation. These skills include social and emotional support as well as cognitive and practical information that is necessary to enhance teaching practices (Day 2004). Programs for professional development are frequently provided as a specific formal endeavour, supported by cooperative methods that help educators learn new concepts, reflect on, and deepen "their commitment as change agents to the moral purposes of teaching" (Day 1999:4). This is reflected in the notion that teachers acquire knowledge through participating in particular activities, like in-service training, during designated study periods (Opfer & Pedder 2011). Short-term activities like conferences are frequently seen as cooperative initiatives meant to advance teachers' expertise and methods in the classroom (Lundgren, Scheckle & Zinn 2015). Scholars such as Brodie et al. (2002) and Lundgren et al. (2015) contend that formal professional development programs may or may not result in teacher learning or instructional modifications. We also recognize that teacher learning can occur from a variety of activities, including informal learning, collaborative communities, and structured programs. A teacher's ability to "shape their own professional development and positive changes through reflective participation in professional programmes and in practise" is demonstrated by Clarke and Hollingsworth's (2002) teacher growth model (1948). The character of each teacher's professional development and educational changes is determined by the interaction of several elements within their zones of influence, as the writers affirm. The way that complexity theory views teacher learning—which is a dynamic process influenced by three systems—conforms with these conceptualizations (individual teacher, the educational setting, and external input. According to Opfer and Pedder (2011), these systems are made up of subsystems that "combine differently from one person to another and at various situations." Thus, simply going to workshops or professional development events won't be sufficient to alter teaching strategies. Our study is based on these intricate conceptual understandings of professional development and teacher transformation.

5. RESEARCH DESIGN

This study uses a qualitative methodology, which is common to descriptive case studies (Yin 2009), to investigate how one teacher teaches oral language development to learners in Grade 12. The teacher's perceptions and experiences of how the ACE program affected her teaching style are also discussed in the study. We are aware that the generalizability of case studies is criticized. Nonetheless, a case's strengths lie in its capacity to produce a detailed description within a given context by utilizing a variety of evidence (Simons 2009; Yin 2009). Thus, individual situations such as ours can be realized in comparable circumstances or ideas, and in combination they may serve as the foundation for future ongoing studies.

6. CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

The province of the Free State, which has both urban and rural populations, serves as the study's background. 54 kilometres from Bloemfontein, the school is situated in the midst of a township, or black residential area, in Botshabelo. This public school is free of charge and has permanent buildings along with standard classroom supplies like whiteboards, teaching aids, and student desks and chairs. The majority of learners come from low-income families and depend on the federal school lunch program to increase their attendance. The language of teaching for 99% of FETP participants is Sesotho, which is also their home language.

7. THE PARTICIPANT

Disebo (pseudonym) is a mid-30s African woman who graduated from high school in 2001. Prior to transferring to Grade 12, Disebo spent several years as a Grade 10 teacher at the township school. She earned her first professional credential, the (PD), while working part-time. In 2010, she also finished a brief course on life orientation teaching techniques. 42 and 44 learners were enrolled in Disebo's classes during the 2017–2018 data collection period. Disebo stated that she participated in over five DBE workshops on FETP instruction between 2011 and 2013. Based on our observations and conversations, Disebo presented herself as an innovative and self-driven achiever. The self-designed posters, the vibrant and well-organized learning area, and the assortment of posters—the majority of which had labels in both HL and FETP served as proof of this. She demonstrated an inventive and driven attitude by designing study guides for each of her pupils.

8. DATA COLLECTION

The information analyzed was a component of a PhD project that looked at the professional development of two teachers in Grade 12 who were specifically chosen. In order to have a deeper knowledge of the experiences and implementation of one teacher, Author 1 went back and reviewed the PhD data for this work. The objective was to ascertain whether any pedagogical changes may have been attributed to the ACE program. As a result, in order to investigate Disebo's instructional strategies for teaching oral language during HL classes, only her data was re-examined. Six classroom recordings, interviews, and field notes were among the 18 months' worth of data that were gathered from 2017 to 2018.

9. DATA ANALYSIS

The pedagogical adjustments and resource utilization are understood in this paper through the lens of the FETP teaching HL concepts. The intended curriculum of the ACE program upholds these ideals. To comprehend oral language education and the potential impact of the ACE program on any modifications to videotaped or in-person observed teaching methods, two types of analyses were conducted. First off, Disebo's statements from the interviews and observation field notes were used to support her account, which was created after closely examining the video transcripts. Disebo confirmed the tale and the changes. The narrative illuminated Disebo's knowledge and skills that she claimed to have learnt from the ACE programme about oral language teaching and how the programme impacted her teaching. Secondly, to analyse Disebo's oral language teaching and use of resources, we created specific episodes of the lessons from the video transcripts which were deductively scored against a set of indicators. The 12 key indicators presented in Table 1 below were generated from the five principles of teaching HL according to the ACE programme. We used the indicators to make sense of the teacher's talks, interaction with the learners, peer conversations and use of resources during the lesson (Kimathi, 2017).

Principles of teaching HL	Indicators of good practice which were used as analytic tools
To be bilingual, one must acquire both HL and EFAL.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage bilingualism by, for instance, using meaningful code-switching to improve dialogue. • Genuine education, amiable, captivating, critical thinking, etc.
Theories that affect how HL is taught (both naturally and formally)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching HL's grammatically sound structures and applying formal methods. • Based on Krashen's concept, contextual and informal possibilities for learners to inadvertently absorb HL.
Increasing one's vocabulary and fluency in spoken sentences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make use of both spoken and nonverbal tools, such as role-playing, puppets, reading aloud, and drawings. • Formal vocabulary learning, such as labelling classroom supplies, giving instructions directly, teaching themes, encouraging wide reading, and so forth.
Develop and put to use techniques and resources that encourage in-depth reading and enhance writing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Make use of balanced reading strategies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give students the chance to interact meaningfully with words. • Set a positive example for handwriting and observe students' notes and sketches.
An atmosphere rich in print that promotes writing, spelling, and reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Make use of a variety of books, images, imaginative displays, and sight words: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collections that are tailored to the individual needs of learners. • A school library or an accessible reading and discussion area, among other options.

TABLE 1: Advanced Certificate in Teaching programme intended curriculum in relation to teaching Sesotho as Home Language at the FET Phase. Source: Adopted from (Kimathi, 2017)

10. FINDINGS

Disebo attests that a number of factors—not all of which are equally explicit—influenced her choice of words. Authenticity and research integrity are the primary goals here, which are attained by attempting to match the language used during fieldwork with the language used in the research report. It is noteworthy in and of itself that the parents answered the bilingual Disebo questionnaire in Sesotho. The decision to use one's native tongue as a medium of instruction signifies a tiny moment of empowerment in an educational setting when English is so prevalent. Even though it seems misguided to rule out the possibility of translation, Disebo's claim that "if I had written it in English I would have a different product, it would not have been what they were saying" raises the possibility that something important was lost in translation because language was a key factor in the dispute.

Second, Ms. Y states that she decided to utilize English for some parts of the course since the instructor, whose lack of Sesotho proficiency is subtly implied but not explicitly stated, is one of her students. It's also an interested position because Ms. Disebo wanted to hear the more knowledgeable lecturer's thoughts on her draft; her choice to discuss the readings in their native language (English) and to quote from them is therefore a calculated tactic to get feedback. By doing this, Ms. Disebo can be confident that both lecturers will give her their entire attention, and she can effectively play to both of their talents. Thus, Ms. Disebo's task is a powerful testament to her pragmatic nature and her bilingual repertoire in the same domain.

The replies above demonstrate how well-received Sesotho was by ACE participants when it came to instruction, classroom interaction, course notes, and assessment both verbally and in writing. It is noteworthy, nevertheless, that educators believed having choices was crucial. People valued the opportunity to choose the language used for their assessments. People who selected Sesotho reported relief at being freed from the constraints of English, allowing them to engage freely and improve their performance. Naturally, this does not indicate that the serious issue of instructors' inadequate conceptual expertise (Taylor & Vinjevod, 1999) has been resolved; merely changing the tuition's language does not ensure a high standard of instruction. It does imply that one obstacle to epistemic access is thereby overcome by expanding the language of tuition alternatives to include the mother tongue.

11. CONCLUSIONS

When they are allowed to assimilate information and negotiate meaning in the language, they are most familiar with, teachers and students alike find their voices and grow in confidence. Given the backdrop of centuries of colonial practice and the marginalization of African languages, being granted the option to do so is a minor success in the fight for mother tongue based bilingual education (MTBBE). Sesotho's potential as a language of enskilling in accredited teacher development—a high-status field usually designated for English and Afrikaans is signalled by its usage as a language of instruction and evaluation on the ACE course. There is no denying the subjective aspect of empowerment in the narratives discussed above. There is little doubt that learning African languages as a teacher prepares students for greater cognition, but also for the relief that comes from being able to "feel at home" in a language they are familiar with. The monolingual habitus in general and the standard language ideology in particular are challenged when two languages are used in a single written assignment (Stroud, 2002). In a multilingual setting when the majority of teachers speak an African language first and the majority of materials are still in English, it also attests to the pragmatic "readiness for action" aspect of language attitudes (Baker, 1992).

The successful, albeit sporadic, use of isiXhosa in the course highlights the need to match the language(s) of instruction with the WCED Language Transformation Plan. It is expected of teachers to use in the classroom. In the words of a 2009 WCED evaluation of the ACE, "The ACE course should model its message." A few instructors tried their best to co-teach and took assignments in isiXhosa. Refusing to do this can send a strong message to the pupils about how much you value their language.

In an organized MTBBE program, valuing the mother tongue is a crucial, if difficult, task. It will call for modifications to institutional language policy, changes in language attitudes, and staffing investments, including external moderation), in addition to instructional materials and learning tools used across the curriculum—that is, language development at the corpus, status, and acquisition planning levels. If MTBBE is to be realized, significant investments in African languages at the teacher training level will be necessary for the foreseeable future. However, these investments must be balanced against the "counterfactual," or the expense of not making these investments and carrying on as usual (Grin, 2005).

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